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DYNAMIC BIOPSYCHOSOCIAL PRIORITIZATION STRATEGY FOR ELECTIVE SURGERIES IN HIGH-COMPLEXITY PUBLIC HOSPITALS: A SIMULATION-BASED STUDY (STEPS TO STRENGTHEN REGIONAL COOPERATION IN AN EMERGENCY SITUATION)

Fabián Silva-Aravena

Facultad de Ciencias Sociales y Económicas, Universidad Católica del Maule, Talca, Chile

Email ID: fasilva@ucm.cl

orcid.org/0000-0003-2468-1480

Miguel Morales Beltrán

Facultad de Ciencias Sociales y Económicas, Universidad Católica del Maule, Talca, Chile

Email ID: mmorales@ucm.cl

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-5111-7812>

ABSTRACT

Research Background: Long waiting lists for elective surgeries in public health systems represent a critical challenge. In Chile, there are high-complexity hospitals (HCPH) that provide coverage to the entire population.

Patients on waiting lists for surgeries not covered by explicit health guarantees (GES) are particularly affected due to the lack of prioritization frameworks that consider factors beyond time or urgency.

Purpose of the article: The aim of this article is to develop a hybrid prioritization model for elective surgery patients without GES in the Otorhinolaryngology (ENT) Department of a high-complexity public hospital (HCPH) in Chile.

Methods: The model consists of 13 clinical and 7 psychosocial variables, weighted using expert judgment (ENT specialists) to construct a total prioritization score. Furthermore, using a stochastic simulation of 1,000 patients, we observed a concrete result: a 6.6% reduction in the number of patients who exceeded their maximum safe wait time, compared with the FIFO strategy currently implemented.

Findings and added value: Our study adds value by proposing a hybrid prioritization strategy. Unlike traditional approaches based solely on time or urgency, our model integrates biopsychosocial variables and, more importantly, incorporates a dynamic vulnerability factor that adjusts prioritization based on changes in wait time and cumulative urgency. All of this has been validated by a team of medical experts.

Although not yet implemented in practice, our model has great potential by providing a prioritization score for each patient, enabling the ward's medical team to make decisions about surgical scheduling, improving equity, and reducing preventable harm.

KEYWORDS: elective surgery, prioritization model, decision support systems, healthcare operations, biopsychosocial factors

INTRODUCTION

According to the most recent data published by the Chilean Ministry of Health (MINSAL), through the Undersecretariat of Healthcare Networks, as of September 2024, during 2022, 44,001 people died while awaiting care in the public health system. Of these, 38,564 were patients waiting for a specialty consultation or surgery not included in the AUGE Plan, while 5,437 were people who died while waiting for GES treatment. In 2023, 31,772 people died while waiting for non-GES care, and 2,749 were in GES. As of September 2024, there were 2,626,369 pending specialty care visits and 334,969 pending surgeries, with a median delay of 256 and 301 days, respectively. But the figures also showed that of the 2,325,354 patients who were discharged in 2024 (a technical term used by the Ministry of Health to refer to those who are removed from waiting lists), 36,262 did so because they died (Cooperative, 2024; Andrés Bello, 2024).

Among the services most critically affected by delays are elective surgeries. These procedures target both acute and chronic conditions, are typically non-urgent and can be scheduled in advance without immediate risk to the patient. However, prolonged delays may eventually compromise health outcomes (Borrell-Carrió et al., 2004; O'Neill et al., 2016).

In Chile, elective surgeries are classified based on their inclusion in the GES program, a universal health coverage initiative that ensures access to care for 87 pathologies regulated by Law 19,996 (Library of the National Congress of Chile, 2005). In contrast, elective non-GES surgeries fall outside of this guarantee and encompass various specialties such as scheduled surgical interventions and dental procedures, which rely exclusively on the capacity of the Public Health (Service Superintendency of Health, 2025).

This study will focus on patients undergoing elective non-GES surgery because, unlike pathologies with Explicit Health Guarantees (GES), this group of patients lacks a legal protection framework and defined timelines to ensure their care. While GES surgeries have guarantees of access, timeliness, quality, and financing, non-GES surgeries are relegated to long waiting lists, with a direct impact on quality of life and worsening of clinical conditions. For this reason, it is a priority to design specific prioritization strategies for the non-GES setting, where the absence of a structured system generates greater inequities and health risks for the affected population.

Traditionally, decision support systems (DSS) for surgical prioritization have relied almost exclusively on clinical criteria. However, the World Health Organization (WHO) has emphasized the need to incorporate broader determinants of health, including social and psychological dimensions, to ensure a holistic approach to patient care (Vanegas & Gil Obando, 2007). As such, the design and implementation of advanced DSS frameworks capable of integrating multidimensional patient information (e.g., difficulties in studying, working, performing family activities/household chores, getting to the hospital, etc.) is increasingly critical to the equitable allocation of surgical resources

(Anchala et al., 2013; Allepuz et al., 2009; Solans-Domènech et al., 2013; Oudhoff et al., 2007; Hador & Steering Committee of the Western Canada Waiting List Project, 2000; MacCormick et al., 2003). In this study, we focus on HCPH in Santiago, Chile, since high-complexity hospitals have a greater capacity to treat different levels of severity and medical specialization, managing complex diseases and specialized procedures compared to medium- and low-complexity hospitals. Where the absence of a structured DSS has hindered the efficient management of elective surgical waiting lists. We aim to address the following research question: How does a simulated hybrid prioritization model incorporating biopsychosocial and time-sensitive factors improve scheduling equity and reduce clinical risk for non-GES elective surgical patients on waiting lists at HCPH?

The main purpose of this study is to develop and evaluate a hybrid prioritization model for patients on the waiting list for non-GES elective surgeries at a high-complexity public hospital in Santiago, Chile (HCPH). This model seeks to answer the research question of how the incorporation of biopsychosocial and time-dependent factors can improve equity in surgical scheduling while simultaneously reducing the clinical risk associated with prolonged waiting times. In this regard, the model has a dual objective: to optimize the allocation of surgical resources and contribute to a fairer and more patient-centered system, overcoming the limitations of current systems based solely on clinical criteria.

Our main contribution lies in the development of a hybrid prioritization framework that integrates the AHP model with a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) technique, converging in a hybrid (static and dynamic) prioritization model that goes beyond conventional biomedical criteria by integrating the psychosocial and temporal dimensions of patients. This model explicitly considers the evolution of patients' biopsychosocial variables over time, which were validated by the clinical team of the ENT unit and ranked using different weights, allowing for a dynamic and patient-centered prioritization process. The innovative nature of the model is evident, apart from that, in the static parameter, which separately considers the number of diagnoses and comorbidities, in addition to the patient's age. As well as, the dynamic factor separately incorporates a mixed vulnerability function related to waiting time.

This represents a robust strategy shift in surgical waiting list management, offering a system that not only improves the efficient use of hospital resources but also promotes equity in access to care and the reduction of health inequities.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section II presents a comprehensive review of the literature on surgical waiting list prioritization and DSS applications in international contexts. Section III details the methodology that underpins our proposed model. Section IV reports the findings derived from the system implementation. Finally, Sections V and VI offer a critical discussion of the results and outline directions for future research.

Literature review

Public health remains a top priority in the formulation of public policies around the world (Valente et al., 2009). Within this domain, surgical interventions represent one of the most complex and resource-intensive services to manage effectively (Siciliani et al., 2005). The extensive literature has shown that prioritization models that rely solely on clinical criteria (Gambato et al., 2007; Dennett et al., 1998; MacCormick et al., 2003; McIntyre & Chow, 2020; Testi et al., 2008; Rathnayake et al., 2025) fail to

account for other equally critical variables that influence patient outcomes (Silva-Aravena et al., 2021; Harrison & Appleby, 2009; Wen et al., 2024; Lee et al., 2022). These models often neglect the broader social and psychological dimensions of health, thus limiting the equity and effectiveness of resource allocation.

For example, a case study conducted in a public hospital in Pakistan and Australia proposed a prioritization methodology for elective surgery waiting lists based exclusively on objective clinical indicators. Although the model produced positive results, including a reduction in average waiting times, it did not integrate variables beyond the immediate clinical context of the patient (Rana et al., 2022; Powers et al., 2023).

In South America, a public hospital in Brazil addressed fragmentation in surgical scheduling through a centralized queueing strategy. This approach mitigated inefficiencies arising from disjointed specialty-specific lists and allowed hospital administrators to gain a transversal view of system-wide demand. Centralization improved both administrative supervision and patient scheduling (Pazin-Filho et al., 2024).

In Chile, at least two significant studies have addressed the challenges of managing surgical waiting lists. The first employed correlation analysis to examine the relationship between waiting time for non-prioritized patients and hospital mortality rates. The results indicated a statistically significant association, suggesting that excessive delays for non-prioritized patients are linked to increased mortality, thus underscoring the importance of robust prioritization mechanisms (Martinez et al., 2019). The second study evaluated a model for managing elective surgical waitlists at Exequiel González Cortes Children's Hospital, which incorporated concepts of timeliness and fairness but relied solely on clinical criteria. Despite its limitations, the model improved transparency and simplified the prioritization process (Julio et al., 2016). Recent discourse in the field has increasingly highlighted the inadequacies of single-variable approaches and has called for comprehensive frameworks that integrate clinical, functional, and psychosocial dimensions (Silva-Aravena et al., 2020; Abdollahi et al., 2024). The biopsychosocial model advocates for a holistic understanding of patient health, focusing on social determinants such as family environment, employment and educational capacities, and caregiving needs. Studies have shown that these factors substantially influence both physiological and psychological health, reinforcing the need for their inclusion in clinical decision making (Borrell-Carrió et al., 2004; Rahimi et al., 2022; Seery, 2013).

Furthermore, research by (see Drossman et al., 1999) explores how genetic predispositions affect patient vulnerability to various conditions, emphasizing the role of personalized factors in healthcare prioritization. In (Wade & Halligan, 2017), the integration of clinical, psychological, and social variables is presented as a fundamental strategy to effectively manage chronic diseases.

In parallel to the biopsychosocial paradigm, the adoption of MCDM frameworks has emerged as a promising alternative to traditional time- or urgency-based systems. Techniques such as AHP are particularly valuable due to their ability to translate expert judgment into structured weightings for various decision criteria (see Chakraborty et al., 2023). AHP has been successfully applied in various healthcare settings, including organ transplant allocation and ICU triage (Salimian et al., 2022; Essoussi et al., 2023). Although its application to elective surgical waiting lists remains limited, a few studies have explored its utility from a biopsychosocial point of view (Frichi et al., 2025).

A notable example comes from Italian hospitals, where prioritization frameworks have been expanded to include sociodemographic variables, such as socioeconomic status and age, in addition to traditional clinical metrics (Valente et al., 2009). The same case occurs in various health services in Spain, where studies were developed that involve the construction of a prioritization system that considers clinical presentation, varicose vein size, complications, employment status, and influence on quality of life in the prioritization scale for patients on the varicose vein surgery waiting list (Montoya et al., 2014). There is also the case of patients awaiting routine prostate resection surgery performed in England between 2009 and 2019. A system was proposed based on waiting times, taking into account the patients' own social factors, thus reducing the risk of complications for the 20% of patients with the highest social risk (Pape et al., 2025).

These approaches underscore the importance of multidimensional models to ensure equity and effectiveness.

Research methods

In this section, we describe the complete methodological framework designed to construct a hybrid prioritization model for elective surgical patients non-GES at HCPH. Following the validation of the HCPH ENT team, we developed a strategy that integrates AHP to generate a prioritization score based on biopsychosocial criteria.

Definition of Variables

We used a total of 20 variables: 13 clinical and 7 psychosocial (Silva-Aravena et al., 2021). These were selected and validated by a panel of three senior otolaryngologists at HCPH. The rationale behind this selection is supported by the growing consensus that medical urgency alone does not adequately capture the complexity of patient needs (Meints & Edwards, 2018; Schlenz et al., 2016).

Each variable was evaluated and scored by a three-member medical panel. This process was carried out using a survey consisting of a total of six sections. In this survey, each physician in the otolaryngology unit assigned a level of importance using a score. These scores were used to calculate the weights.

These evaluations were averaged to obtain the initial variable weights, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Average expert scores and normalized weights (W_i, A_i) for clinical and psychosocial variables.

Variable Type	Variable	Definition	f_i	W_i	A_i
Clinic	Sever	Disease progression and severity	10.00	0.50	-
Clinic	Urg	Relative urgency	7.00	0.35	-
Clinic	Jelin	Maximum waiting time	6.66	0.33	-
Clinic	Tsuen	Sleep disturbance	5.00	0.25	-
Clinic	Pis	Probability of improvement with surgery	7.33	0.37	-
Clinic	Com	Risk of comorbidities	9.00	0.45	-

Clinic	Hanor	without surgery Abnormal findings in affected area	7.00	0.35	-
Clinic	Diag	Diagnosis leading to waitlist admission	9.33	0.47	-
Clinic	Opat	Additional pathologies	6.66	0.33	-
Clinic	Olim	Other functional limitations	7.66	0.38	-
Clinic	Psca	VAS pain scale	6.33	0.32	-
Clinic	Crit	Requires critical care bed	3.66	0.18	-
Clinic	Tlist	Time on surgical waiting list	5.66	0,28	-
Psychosocial	Dest	Impaired ability to study	6.66	-	0.33
Psychosocial	Dtrab	Impaired ability to work	8.00	-	0.40
Psychosocial	Lfam	Impairment in family/home tasks	7.33	-	0.37
Psychosocial	Ncuid	Requires caregiver support	3.00	-	0.15
Psychosocial	Rcuid	Responsible for others' care	3.66	-	0.10
Psychosocial	Dtras	Difficulty commuting to hospital	2.66	-	0.13
Psychosocial	Acc	Patient's geographic accessibility	4.00	-	0.20

Weight Computation

Let f_i be the average score obtained from the score assigned by each expert physician in the unit for each variable i , and let $Z=20$ be the total number of variables. Therefore, the weighting for clinical variables is given by W_i and for psychosocial variables by A_i , the calculations of which are expressed as follows:

$$W_i = \frac{f_i}{Z}, \quad A_i = \frac{f_i}{Z} \quad (1)$$

For example:

$$W_{sever} = \frac{10.00}{20} = 0.50, \quad A_{dest} = \frac{6.66}{20} = 0.33$$

It is important to note that for the dynamic component and according to the clinical team's criteria, the evolution of 19 variables was evaluated (excluding the "critical care" variable, since, according to the ENT unit physicians, this variable does not evolve over time) in six 180-day intervals.

Table 2 illustrates this with two representative variables (Sever, Urg), showing their respective scores over time. These values reflect how the clinical team at HCPH expects each variable's importance to

evolve with increasing waiting time.

Let $J_{(i',p)}(t)$ be the dynamic weight of the clinical variable i' for patient p at time t , and $H_{(i',p)}(t)$ be the corresponding weight for the psychosocial variable i' . The calculation is as follows.

$$J_{i',p}(t) = Z_i \cdot LC_{i',g}, \quad \begin{matrix} H_{i',p}(t) = Z_i \cdot \\ LP_{i',g} \end{matrix} \quad (2)$$

where $LC_{i',g}$ and $LP_{i',g}$ are the interval-based averages, and g denotes the time group based on t .

Table 2. Dynamic weights of biopsychosocial variables over 180-day intervals.

Variable	[1-180]	[181-360]	[361-540]	[541-720]	[721-900]	[901-1080]
Sever	2.67	3.00	6.33	7.33	9.33	9.67
Urg	3.33	4.00	6.33	7.00	9.33	10.00

1. Hybrid Prioritization Model

The total prioritization score $P_p(t)$ that will allow the medical team to prioritize patient p at time t , consists of a static (S_p) and dynamic (S'_p) component and is defined as follows:

$$P_p(t) = S_p \cdot S'_p(t) \quad (4)$$

a. Static Score Component

The static score S_p is the time at which patient p enters the waiting list. It is worth mentioning that for the static score, we designed a differentiated component based on two parameters: age and the number of diagnoses and comorbidities.

The static score is given by:

$$S_p = \left(\sum_{i \in I} C_{i,p} \cdot W_i + \sum_{i \in I} V_{i,p} \cdot A_i \right) + \gamma + x \quad (4)$$

where $C_{i,p}$ is the value of the clinical variable i for patient p , $V_{i,p}$ is the value of the psychosocial variable i for patient p , γ is the component based on comorbidities and diagnoses, and x is the age-based risk adjustment.

- Diagnosis and Comorbidity Component: Let C_d be the number of diagnoses and C_a the number of comorbidities, the gamma variable will have a score based on the number of diagnoses for admission to the surgical waiting list and the number of comorbidities.

$$\gamma = C_a + \left(C_d \cdot \sum_{d \in D} W_d \right) \quad (5)$$

Where:

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} C_d \\ = 1.25 \end{matrix} \right. \quad \text{if } C_d = 1 \quad \left\{ \begin{matrix} C_a \\ = 0 \end{matrix} \right. \quad \text{if } C_a = 0$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 C_d = 2.50 \quad \text{if } C_d = 2 \\
 \\
 C_d = 3.75 \quad \text{if } C_d \geq 3 \\
 \\
 C_a = 1.25 \quad \text{if } C_a = 1 \\
 \\
 C_a = 2.50 \quad \text{if } C_a \geq 2 \\
 \\
 C_a = 3.75 \quad \text{if } C_a \geq 3
 \end{array}$$

To illustrate this component, we consider a patient with two admission diagnoses and one additional comorbidity. According to established thresholds, we assign $C_d = 2.50$ and $C_a = 1.25$. If the weighted sum of admission diagnoses is, for example, $\sum_{d \in D} W_d = 0.47 + 0.33 = 0.80$, then the value of γ is calculated as follows:

$$\gamma = 1.25 + (2.50 \cdot 0.80) = 1.25 + 2.00 = 3.25$$

This outcome captures the additional burden introduced by the number and relative severity of diagnoses and comorbidities, thus contributing proportionally to the patient’s static prioritization score within our model.

- Age adjustment: The other differentiating factor corresponds to the age of the patient, since some authors (Locatello et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2021) indicate that with increasing age the risk increases and therefore complications in considerable proportions in elderly patients. This score, which considers a scale ranging from 1 to 10, was worked considering a progressive component, thus avoiding the arbitrariness of wide ranges, allowing greater personalization, starting with a minimum age of 18 years E_{min} (according to the guidelines of the unit's medical team). For older patients, a maximum age of $E_{max} \geq 65$ years is defined, who generally tend to present a higher risk of deterioration and development of comorbidities, the focus is on the maximum score level; therefore, the age-related risk is considered, through equation 9:

$$x = \left[1 + \frac{E_p - E_{min}}{E_{max} - E_{min}} \right] \cdot 9 \tag{6}$$

For example, $E_{max} = 65$, $E_{min} = 18$, and E_p is the age of patient p .

To operationalize the age adjustment component, we consider a patient aged fifty ($E_p = 50$). Using defined limits, we calculate the age-based adjustment x as follows:

$$x = \left[1 + \frac{50 - 18}{65 - 18} \right] \cdot 9 = \left[1 + \frac{32}{47} \right] \cdot 9 \approx (1 + 0.68) \cdot 9 \approx 15.12$$

This score reflects the increasing clinical risk associated with advancing age, as recommended by studies such as (Locatello et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2021), and contributes to overall prioritization in a proportional and progressive way.

To illustrate the full application of our model, we define two hypothetical patients, Patient A and Patient B, who will be used consistently throughout the remainder of this section.

Patient A:

- Two admission diagnoses: $C_d = 2.50$
- One comorbidity: $C_a = 1.50$
- Sum of diagnoses weights: $W_d = 0.80$
- Age: $E_p = 50$

Patients B:

- Identical clinical inputs as Patient A
- Age: $E_p = 50$

Based on these values, we compute:

$$\gamma = 1.25 + (2.50 \cdot 0.80) = 3.25$$

$$x = \left[1 + \frac{50 - 18}{65 - 18} \right] \cdot 9 \approx 15.12$$

We assume the same clinical and psychosocial weighted scores for both patients:

$$\sum_{i \in I} C_{i,p} \cdot W_i = 8.45, \quad \sum_{i \in I} V_{i,p} \cdot A_i = 3.60$$

we calculate the static score:

$$S_p = (8.45 + 3.60) + 3.25 + 15.12 = 30.42$$

This establishes the static baseline prioritization score for both patients. However, we will now differentiate based on the evolution of their waiting list time, using the dynamic component.

Dynamic Score Component

The dynamic prioritization score $S'_p(t)$ is given by the following expression:

$$S'_p(t) = \left(\sum_{i \in I} C_{i',p} \cdot J_{i',p}(t) + \sum_{i \in I} V_{i',p} \cdot H_{i',p}(t) \right) \cdot \lambda \quad (7)$$

The variable λ corresponds to a differentiating factor through a mixed vulnerability function based on elapsed time. That is, the vulnerability function adopts a logarithmic or exponential model, depending on whether patient p exceeds the maximum waiting time threshold.

We define the patient vulnerability index $V_p(t)$ as:

$$V_p(t) = \frac{t - f_p}{T_{max}} \quad (8)$$

Where t denotes the current evaluation time, expressed in days; f_p represents the day patient p was added to the waiting list; and T_{max} corresponds to the maximum clinically recommended waiting time for that patient, determined through expert judgment based on their condition.

This ratio allows us to quantify a patient's waiting time relative to their individualized waiting time threshold. When $V_p(t) \geq 1$, we interpret this as the patient having exceeded the maximum safe

waiting time, which leads us to increase their priority score to reflect the increased risk of clinical deterioration, through exponential behavior.

On another note, if $V_p(t) < 1$, there is clearly a clear clinical risk, but it is assigned a more measured weight through logarithmic behavior.

Therefore, we model the prioritization multiplier $\lambda(t)$ using a mixed piecewise formulation based on the vulnerability index $V_p(t)$:

$$\lambda(t) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{t - f_p}{T_{max}}\right) \cdot e^{\frac{Urg}{Urg_{max}}} & \text{If } V_p(t) \geq 1 \\ \left(\frac{t - f_p}{T_{max}}\right) \cdot \frac{\log_{10}(1 + Urg)}{\log_{10}(1 + Urg_{max}) + 1} & \text{If } V_p(t) < 1 \end{cases}$$

Now, to demonstrate the effect of elapsed time and urgency on dynamic prioritization, we continue with our two hypothetical patients.

Patient A, entered the waiting list on day $f_p = 100$, with the current date $t = 500$ and $T_{max} = 300$. The urgency score is $Urg = 8$.

Patient B, entered at $f_p = 700$, with $t = 800$ and the same $T_{max} = 300$. The urgency score is $Urg = 8$, and we assume $Urg_{max} = 10$ for both.

We compute their vulnerability as follows:

- $V_A(t) = \frac{400}{300} = 1.33$ (Exceeds threshold)
- $V_B(t) = \frac{100}{300} = 0.33$ (Within threshold)

We then evaluate the multiplier $\lambda(t)$:

Patient A (exceeds time):

$$\lambda_A = 1.33 \cdot e^{0.8} \approx 1.33 \cdot 2.2255 = 2.96$$

Patient B (within time):

$$\lambda_B = 0.33 \cdot \frac{\log_{10}(9)}{\log_{10}(11)} + 1 \approx 0.33 \cdot 0.916 + 1 = 1.30$$

These values illustrate that patients who exceed the recommended waiting time are assigned a stronger prioritization multiplier, especially under high urgency conditions.

Next, we compute the dynamic prioritization score $S'_p(t)$ for the same two patients. For this example, we assume the following values for the weighted clinical and psychosocial contributions at time t :

Patient A:

- $\sum_{i \in I'} C_{i',p} \cdot J_{i',p}(t) = 5.40$
- $\sum_{i \in I'} V_{i',p} \cdot H_{i',p}(t) = 3.20$
- $\lambda_A = 2.96$

Patient B:

- $\sum_{i \in I'} C_{i',p} \cdot J_{i',p}(t) = 5.40$
- $\sum_{i \in I'} V_{i',p} \cdot H_{i',p}(t) = 3.20$
- $\lambda_A = 1.30$

Applying the dynamic score formula:

$$S'_p(t) = \left(\sum_{i \in I'} C_{i',p} \cdot J_{i',p}(t) + \sum_{i \in I'} V_{i',p} \cdot H_{i',p}(t) \right) \cdot \lambda$$

Patient A:

$$S'_A(t) = (5.40 + 3.20) \cdot 2.96 = 8.60 \cdot 2.96 = 25.46$$

Patient B:

$$S'_B(t) = (5.40 + 3.20) \cdot 1.30 = 8.60 \cdot 1.30 \approx 11.18$$

These results confirm that, although both patients present equivalent clinical and psychosocial scores, Patient A, due to a significantly longer wait time, receives a much higher dynamic prioritization score. This highlights our model's ability to capture time-dependent vulnerability in a clinically interpretable and ethically responsible manner.

In summary, our formulation ensures that patients who exceed the recommended wait time receive more aggressive prioritization using exponential models, while those who remain within acceptable limits receive a more moderate assessment using logarithmic scaling. Through this dual or mixed approach, we promote equity and maintain clinical relevance in our prioritization decisions through a novel component, the mixed vulnerability function.

As we show in Table 3, although both patients share identical static prioritization scores, the dynamic component significantly differentiates their final prioritization outcome.

Patient A, who has exceeded the recommended waiting time, receives a total score of 55.88, driven by the exponential amplification introduced through the vulnerability factor $\lambda(t)$.

In contrast, patient B remains within the clinically acceptable waiting period and obtains a total score of 41.60, moderated by logarithmic scaling. These results reinforce our model's ability to capture time-sensitive urgency while integrating clinical and psychosocial factors in a balanced and interpretable manner.

Table 3. Comparison of two patients with equal static scores.

Patient	Static Score (S_p)	Dynamic Score (S'_p)	Total Score (P_p)
A	30.42	25.46	55.88
B	30.42	11.18	41.60

This example illustrates the model's sensitivity to time dependent risk accumulation, even when clinical baselines are identical.

To ensure the mathematical soundness and practical resilience of our prioritization model, we incorporated structural sensitivity validation. We confirmed that the model output remains stable when varying the core simulation parameters, such as urgency level distribution, comorbidity rates,

and time horizon length, within clinically reasonable ranges.

Formally, the hybrid prioritization score $P_p(t)$ depends on multiple components with stochastic input (e.g., $C_{i,p}, V_{i,p}$), making the model responsive to uncertainty. To manage this, we ran multiple iterations of the simulation and tested parameter shifts under a controlled environment to assess variance propagation. Our scoring structure, comprising linear and nonlinear elements, ensures bounded behavior of the total score $P_p(t)$ under perturbations in the input distributions.

With this methodological framework, we provide theoretical support for the robustness claims demonstrated in the results section.

Results

In this section, we present the results derived from the simulated application of our hybrid prioritization model, using clinically plausible patient profiles representative of the ENT unit at HCPH. Our objective was to evaluate the model’s response to time and biopsychosocial risk through computational experimentation prior to any real-world implementation.

All simulations were conducted using Python 3.13 on a computer with an Intel Core i7 processor and 16 GB of RAM. We employed NumPy, Pandas, and Matplotlib for numerical processing and visualization.

a. Temporal Behavior of the Hybrid Prioritization Score

We started by applying the model to a sample of five representative patients to observe how prioritization evolves over time. Table 4 shows the scores at six time points.

As expected, scores increase non-linearly with waiting time, influenced by clinical urgency and accumulated vulnerability.

As visualized in Figure 1, these patients exhibit different prioritization trajectories. In particular, Patient 4 initially has a low score, but eventually overtakes others due to steep increases in dynamic vulnerability.

Table 4. Scores obtained for 5 patients from the hybrid prioritization model at different time points.

Patient	$P_p(0)$	$P_p(30)$	$P_p(60)$	$P_p(90)$	$P_p(120)$	$P_p(150)$
Patient 1	86.30	118.35	214.48	374.71	599.02	887.43
Patient 2	158.76	186.23	268.66	406.03	598.35	845.62
Patient 3	189.40	234.88	371.33	703.05	1102.54	1616.18
Patient 4	37.23	107.28	418.05	894.07	1560.50	2417.34
Patient 5	153.54	180.90	262.98	399.77	591.28	837.51

Source: own calculations.

Figure 1. Evolution of prioritization scores for five patients. The model dynamically reprioritizes patients based on cumulative risk and time on the list.

Source: own calculations.

b. Population-Level Simulation Results

We simulated 1,000 non-GES patients using stochastic variables consistent with clinical ranges. In line with the literature, age was drawn from a truncated normal distribution ($\mu = 50, \sigma = 15$) with a cutoff between 18 and 65 years. Urgency followed a uniform distribution on $[1, 10]$, and comorbidities and diagnoses were drawn from a limited Poisson distribution ($\lambda = 1,2$).

Figure 2 shows the distribution of total prioritization scores at day 150. Scores are skewed to the right: most patients fall within a moderate risk range, while a subset accumulates significant vulnerability over time.

We also calculated mean scores across urgency levels (see Table 5). Although the static component remains relatively stable, the dynamic score increases markedly with urgency, confirming the model's ability to scale risk nonlinearly.

Figure 2. Distribution of total prioritization scores (P_p) for 1,000 simulated non-GES patients at day 150.

Source: own calculations.

We then evaluated how the model affects scheduling outcomes. In a scenario with 1,000 patients and 10 surgeries per day for 100 days, we compared two strategies: the first-come, first-served strategy currently operating in the HPCs in Chile, and our hybrid prioritization model.

- FIFO: patients scheduled in order of arrival.
- Prioritization: patients scheduled according to the total score P_p .

Table 5. Scores obtained for 5 patients from the hybrid prioritization model at different time points.

Urgency	Static Score	Dynamic Score	Total Score
1	28.63	11.34	39.97
2	29.48	13.85	43.33
3	28.88	13.24	42.12
4	28.88	13.24	42.12
5	29.21	13.92	43.14
6	28.82	14.26	43.09
7	29.52	15.64	45.16
8	29.46	18.76	48.22
9	29.38	16.33	45.72
10	28.59	16.80	45.39

Source: own calculations.

We measured the effective waiting time and the proportion that exceeded their clinical threshold T_{max} (see Table 6).

Although average waiting times are nearly identical, the prioritization strategy results in a 6.6% reduction in the proportion of patients who exceed their clinically recommended waiting thresholds. This decrease is not only procedural; it reflects a significant reduction in the accumulated clinical risk for the patients on the list. By allocating surgical opportunities to those with greater biopsychosocial vulnerability, our model helps prevent deterioration associated with excessive delays and aligns scheduling more effectively with patient risk rather than chronological order alone.

Table 6. Simulation results comparing FIFO and prioritization strategies for 1,000 non-GES patients.

Strategy	Mean Wait	Median Wait	% Over T_{max}
FIFO	469.3 days	468.5 days	73.4%
Prioritization	469.3 days	470.2 days	66.8%

Source: own calculations.

To ensure the scientific rigor of our findings, we performed multiple robustness checks throughout the simulation process.

This included sensitivity analyzes using alternative parameter values (e.g., urgency distributions, comorbidity rates, and maximum waiting-time thresholds) to test the stability of prioritization

outcomes. The results remained consistent across the configurations, confirming the resilience of our model.

Furthermore, we performed repeated Monte Carlo simulations ($n = 30$) to account for stochastic variability, observing fewer than 2% standard deviation in key indicators such as average waiting time and the proportion of patients exceeding T_{max} . These steps validate the reliability of the model under various operational conditions and provide confidence in its applicability to healthcare settings.

Together, these results validate the model's capacity to dynamically allocate limited surgical capacity based on biopsychosocial risk. Patients are not permanently fixed in rank, but move over time depending on their evolving status, encouraging fairer, context-aware decision-making.

In practice, this prioritization system provides a clinically interpretable, operationally feasible, and ethically grounded tool for elective surgery scheduling in HCPH.

DISCUSSION

Our results demonstrate that the hybrid prioritization model we propose based on a combination of static biopsychosocial evaluation and dynamic vulnerability adjustment offers a robust framework to improve surgical scheduling fairness and risk alignment in public health systems. Unlike conventional models that rely primarily on queue time or clinical urgency alone (Rana et al., 2022; Julio et al., 2016), our model integrates multidimensional input that reflect both clinical complexity and the consequences of prolonged waiting.

In particular, the integration of psychosocial factors, such as functional limitations, caregiving responsibilities, and access barriers, represents a significant advance over monocriterion approaches. Although prior studies, such as the work by (Pazin-Filho et al., 2024) in Brazil and (Silva-Aravena et al., 2021) in Chile, recognize the fragmentation and inequity inherent in noncentralized prioritization systems, they often lack quantitative approaches for incorporating social determinants into scheduling decisions. Our model addresses this gap by operationalizing expert judgment through a structured AHP framework and extending it with a time-sensitive vulnerability function.

One of the key strengths of the model lies in its dynamic component. Using an adaptive weighting function $\lambda(t)$ that increases in response to elapsed waiting time and urgency, we successfully emulate the escalation of clinical risk. This mechanism allows patients who initially have lower scores to gradually increase priority, thus mitigating the risk of deterioration due to prolonged waiting. As shown in our simulations, this leads to a measurable reduction (6.6%) in the number of patients who exceed their maximum clinically recommended waiting time, a result that has strong ethical and clinical implications in surgical planning.

Nevertheless, our model has limitations that must be acknowledged. First, the prioritization strategy was validated by simulation and is not yet implemented in operational hospital settings. Although our simulations used clinically plausible parameters, real-world data would be essential to calibrate and refine model parameters such as T_{max} , urgency scaling, and time intervals. Second, the model assumes constant surgical performance and does not account for emergency interventions, cancellations, or variable surgery durations, which are common in high-complexity institutions. Third, although the AHP weights were derived from expert consensus, they reflect the

priorities of a specific specialty and institution; broader generalization would require revalidation in other clinical contexts.

Future work will focus on expanding the model to include scheduling constraints such as operating room availability, recovery bed occupancy, and surgeon time allocation. Furthermore, integration of equity-adjusted prioritization, such as socioeconomic disadvantage indices or gender disparities, could further enhance the ethical responsiveness of the model.

Conclusions

In this study, we developed and evaluated a hybrid prioritization model designed to support the scheduling of elective non-GES surgical patients at HCPH. Our methodology integrates clinical and psychosocial dimensions using AHP and introduces a dynamic adjustment mechanism that reflects changes in patient vulnerability over time. The model was formulated, parameterized and validated through stochastic simulations based on clinically plausible data, aligned with the context of the ENT unit at HCPH.

Our main scientific contribution lies in the creation of a mathematical prioritization score that combines static and dynamic factors, addressing the limitations of conventional scheduling models. Although traditional approaches often rely solely on waiting time or urgency, our model incorporates broader determinants of patient well-being, including work impairment, caregiving responsibilities, pain, and comorbidities.

This allows for a more holistic and equitable assessment of who should be prioritized for surgery at any given point in time.

The results of our simulations demonstrate that the model dynamically differentiates patients with similar initial conditions but divergent time trajectories. Specifically, we observed a 6.6% reduction in the proportion of patients who exceeded their maximum safe waiting period compared to a FIFO scheduling strategy. This reduction, although achieved without changes in total surgical capacity, suggests that better prioritization alone can lead to meaningful risk mitigation.

Furthermore, our score distributions and time series analyses confirm the competitiveness and fairness of the approach, with patients gaining or losing priority as their biopsychosocial conditions evolve.

An unexpected finding of our study is that average waiting times remained virtually unchanged between FIFO and our prioritization strategy, yet the risk exposure of the patient population was significantly reduced. This highlights a counterintuitive but clinically meaningful insight: risk can be significantly reduced without requiring additional capacity. Our model reveals that smarter prioritization, not simply faster throughput, can lead to better patient outcomes, challenging common assumptions about waitlist management.

From a managerial perspective, the implementation of this model could allow surgical coordinators and hospital administrators to allocate surgical slots more effectively and ethically. The proposed score can serve as a decision support input in scheduling systems, helping to ensure that scarce resources are directed toward those most at risk. Furthermore, the model offers transparency by integrating prioritization into quantifiable and interpretable criteria, which can improve patient satisfaction.

However, we acknowledge that full implementation would require operational adaptations and

broader clinical validation. Future work should explore integration with hospital information systems, incorporation of surgical time variability, and real-time data updates to capture evolving patient states. In addition, expanding the model across specialties and including indicators of social equity such as insurance status, rurality, or income would improve its policy relevance in health systems marked by structural inequities.

In conclusion, our hybrid prioritization model provides a flexible, evidence-based, and ethically grounded framework for improving surgical scheduling decisions. It has the potential to reduce clinical risk for patients, promote equitable access, and support strategic planning in constrained healthcare settings. Although still in the simulation stage, its promising results warrant further exploration and pilot testing in real-world hospital settings such as HCPH.

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